

DFG Collaborative Research Centre 1615

Smart Reactors for Future Process Engineering

Hamburg University of Technology
(TUHH)

TUHH
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RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN HANDBOOK FOR CRC 1615

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Executive Summary

This handbook serves as a foundational framework for each subproject within the Collaborative Research Centre (CRC) 1615 SMART Reactors to develop and deliver their Research Data Management Plan (RDMP) annually. It provides structured directions for managing research data originating from laboratory experiments, field studies, measurements, and simulations. The handbook emphasizes adherence to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) to ensure that RDMPs facilitate data accessibility, quality assurance, and comprehensive documentation to support reuse and maintain research integrity.

Key Messages:

1. **Ten-Year Data Retention:** All research data must be retained for a minimum of ten years to comply with the DFG legal and institutional guidelines. This ensures long-term availability and accountability in research.
2. **Research Data Publication:** Research data underlying publications should be made available for reuse whenever possible and appropriate. If access must be restricted due to legal, ethical, contractual, intellectual property, or technical reasons, these restrictions must be clearly documented in the RDMP.
3. **Open Access:** CRC 1615 encourages open access publication of research outputs whenever possible, using suitable Gold or Green Open Access routes in line with institutional and funder expectations.
4. **Metadata:** Specific metadata must be defined for each data package to ensure the data's discoverability and usability. A minimal example of metadata requirements is provided in the handbook to guide researchers in documenting their data appropriately.
5. **Data Management Plan Compliance:** Subprojects must complete and regularly update their RDMPs in accordance with the guidelines provided in this handbook. This includes addressing data ownership, intellectual property rights, and ensuring data formats are open, standardized, and machine-readable for enhanced long-term accessibility and interoperability.

We have attached an RDMP form for subprojects, which must be completed and regularly updated by responsible researchers in accordance with this handbook. This handbook is reviewed and updated regularly to reflect changes in CRC workflows, TUHH infrastructure, repository options, and funder expectations.

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List of Abbreviations

• CC: Creative Commons
• CRC: Collaborative Research Centre
• DCC: Digital Curation Center
• DFG: Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, German Research Foundation
• DOI: Digital Object Identifier
• ELN: Electronic Lab Notebook
• FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
• FAIR4RS: FAIR Principles for Research Software
• GPL: GNU General Public License
• IP: Intellectual Property
• NFDI: National Research Data Infrastructure
• NFDI4Ing: National Research Data Infrastructure for Engineering Sciences
• ODC: Open Data Commons
• QA/QC: Quality Assurance and Quality Control
• RDA: Research Data Alliance
• RDM: Research Data Management
• RDMP: Research Data Management Plan
• TORE: TUHH Open Research
• TUHH: Technical University of Hamburg
• 5S: Sort, Set in order, Shine, Standardize, Sustain

1. PURPOSE AND SCOPE OF THE HANDBOOK

Digital research data are important outputs of scientific endeavors that require significant investment in terms of finance, time, and expertise for their development. The proliferation of advanced scientific tools has led to an increase in the volume, velocity, veracity, variety, and value of research data, which makes the effective handling of this data much more difficult. Against this background, scientific institutions such as the German Research Foundation (DFG) have continuously imposed requirements on Research Data Management (RDM), as evidenced, for example, by their demand for a detailed description of data management practices in proposals since 2010. Adhering to the FAIR principles—Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable—is essential to ensure that research data are optimally managed and usable by both humans and machines. These principles not only facilitate data preservation and accessibility but also enhance usability and reproducibility, which are key to advancing scientific knowledge and fostering innovation. In our [CRC SMART Reactors](#), each subproject must submit a Research Data Management Plan (RDMP) annually with a deadline of November 30th. Our dedicated data steward assists all subprojects in the preparation of their RDMPs. However, given the interdisciplinary nature of our research, it is crucial for each project to integrate discipline-specific knowledge, as our data steward may not have expertise in all scientific fields represented within the CRC.

Research data are of very high value and their loss cannot be compensated. Therefore, their management, protection, and provision require special attention. It is important to remember that the DFG places a strong emphasis on ensuring research outputs are openly accessible. At the same time, research data underlying publications should be made available for reuse whenever possible and appropriate. If publication or open access is restricted by legal, ethical, contractual, intellectual property, or technical reasons, these restrictions must be documented in the RDMP. This is to ensure that the results are reproducible and that the data can be widely used beyond its original collection, including by stakeholders who were not involved in the original research. Research data encompasses all (digital) data that is the subject, part of research processes (including settings and input parameters), or result of research processes.

This handbook is intended to complement existing guidelines, such as [the Guidelines for Handling Research Data](#) (DFG), [Subject-Specific Recommendations on the Handling of Research Data](#) (DFG), [FAIRMAT Guide to Writing RDMP](#), and [the Codex "Guidelines for Ensuring Good Scientific Practice"](#) (Home | Scientific Integrity). Compliance with these guidelines is mandatory for all subprojects in order to ensure the integrity, accessibility, and reusability of research data. Non-compliance may result in restricted access to shared resources, and potential delays in the project timeline, and may affect the overall success and credibility of the CRC's research outputs. By following these guidelines, compliance with DFG requirements can be ensured, research data can be managed effectively, and the overall success of our CRC can be supported. The principles outlined in this document will help the subprojects within our CRC to align their RDM practices with our overarching goals and standards, thus fostering a collaborative and efficient research environment.

2 CRC 1615 RDM WORKFLOW

RDM in CRC 1615 follows a structured workflow that connects planning, documentation, review, and publication. The aim is to ensure that each subproject maintains an up-to-date RDMP during the active research process and that finalized versions are made findable, citable, and accessible through the CRC's publication infrastructure.

2.1 TUHH DATAPLAN: AN ONLINE TOOL FOR CREATING RDMPs

Each CRC 1615 subproject creates and maintains its RDMP using [TUHH DataPlan](#). The tool supports the structured documentation of key RDM aspects, including data types, data formats, data volume, documentation practices, storage locations, backup procedures, responsibilities, legal considerations, access conditions, and planned publication routes.

The RDMP should be treated as a living document. This means that it should not only be completed once at the beginning of a project, but updated whenever relevant changes occur. Such changes may include new data types, new instruments or software, changes in storage locations, revised responsibilities, new collaboration partners, legal or contractual restrictions, or updated plans for data and software publication.

The Data Steward supports subprojects in preparing, reviewing, and improving their RDMPs. However, each subproject remains responsible for providing accurate discipline-specific information, especially regarding methods, instruments, metadata standards, quality assurance procedures, and reuse conditions.

2.2 PUBLISHING FINALIZED RDMP VERSIONS IN TORE, TUHH'S MAIN REPOSITORY

While TUHH DataPlan is used for creating and updating RDMPs during the research process, finalized or milestone versions of the RDMPs are published via [TORE](#), the institutional repository of TUHH. This supports transparency and makes the CRC's RDM practices visible as part of its research output documentation. Published RDMPs also provide a stable reference point for reporting, review processes, and future reuse of research documentation.

If an RDMP contains sensitive, confidential, legally restricted, or strategically relevant information, the published version should be reviewed before submission to TORE. In such cases, restricted information may need to be removed, generalized, or documented in a non-public internal version.

2.3 ANNUAL REVIEW AND UPDATE PROCESS

Each subproject should review its RDMP at least once per year. The annual review ensures that the plan still reflects the actual research workflow and remains aligned with CRC 1615, TUHH, and DFG expectations.

The annual review should check whether:

- the listed data types and formats are still accurate,
- estimated data volumes need to be updated,
- storage and backup procedures are still valid,
- responsibilities and contact persons are current,
- documentation and metadata practices are sufficient,
- QA/QC procedures are described clearly,
- software, code, and dependencies are documented,
- repository and publication plans are realistic,
- access restrictions, licenses, or embargoes need revision,
- and finalized or milestone versions should be published through TORE.

In addition to the annual review, subprojects should update their RDMP whenever major changes occur. This includes new experiments, new datasets, major methodological changes, new software dependencies, changes in project staff, or decisions regarding data, code, or software publication. This workflow ensures that RDMPs are not static administrative documents, but active planning and documentation instruments that support good research practice throughout the CRC 1615 data lifecycle. The current handbook already defines RDMPs as regularly updated documents and assigns the Data Steward a supporting role for the subprojects, so this section would make that workflow more explicit and publication-ready.

3 GOAL: FAIR PRINCIPLES

The FAIR principles aim to improve the reusability of research data. Data and associated metadata should be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable¹. These principles are aimed at both researchers and infrastructure institutions that establish services for research data. The FAIR principles have been incorporated into the [DFG Code of Conduct for Ensuring Good Scientific Practice](#). The aim is to ensure that research data is optimally prepared and accessible to both humans and machines. This does not mean that every dataset can be reused without restriction. Rather, the FAIR principles aim to open up data sets for new usage scenarios within legal and technical boundaries. The application of the FAIR principles is intended to improve the reusability of data collections. Below our subprojects will find a detailed explanation of these principles and the guidelines for their implementation.

3.1 FINDABLE

For data to be effectively reused, it must first be findable. This requires that both humans and computational systems can easily discover metadata and data. Machine-readable metadata are essential for the automatic discovery of datasets and services.

- (Meta)data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers, ensuring reliable reference and long-term access.
- Data are described with rich metadata, providing comprehensive details about the data's context and structure.
- Metadata explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe, establishing a clear link between data and its metadata.
- (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource, facilitating efficient discovery and access.

3.2 ACCESSIBLE

After finding the necessary data, users must understand how to access it, which may include processes for authentication and authorization.

- (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communication protocol, ensuring consistent and reliable access methods.
 - The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable, promoting broad adoption and interoperability.
 - The protocol supports an authentication and authorization procedure where necessary, ensuring secure access.

¹ FAIR Principles - GO FAIR, Link: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/> Accessed 25 June, 2024

- Metadata remain accessible even if the data are no longer available, preserving the context and information about the data.

3.3 INTEROPERABLE

Data need to be integrated with other datasets and should interoperate with various applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing.

- (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation, ensuring clarity and consistency.
- (Meta)data employ vocabularies that adhere to the FAIR principles, ensuring standardized and interpretable terminology.
- (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data, creating a connected network of information.

3.4 REUSABLE

The ultimate objective of the FAIR principles is to optimize data reuse. This requires that data and metadata are well-described, enabling replication and combination in diverse contexts.

- (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes, providing detailed and relevant contextual information.
- (Meta)data are accompanied by detailed provenance, documenting the origin and history of the data.
- (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license, clarifying the terms of use.
- (Meta)data comply with domain-relevant community standards, ensuring suitability and reliability for specific fields.

The FAIR Guiding Principles², published in 2016 are designed to be integrated into digital infrastructures, and significantly improve the ability of computer systems to cope with the growing volume, complexity, and speed of data creation. In our CRC project, the implementation of the FAIR principles is essential for the management of our research data. Our goal is to ensure that our data is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable by assigning globally unique identifiers, ensuring comprehensive metadata descriptions, and employing standardized communication protocols. This approach not only enhances the usability of our research data but is also in line with best practice in scientific data management and encourages collaboration and innovation within our research communities.

4 FUNDER REQUIREMENTS: DFG

When preparing an RDMP, it is essential to comply with several important requirements set by the DFG³. In accordance with Guideline 13 of the Code of Good Scientific Practice, all research data, materials, and information that form the basis of research results, including the methods used and the software applied, must be made publicly available. Additionally, workflows should be comprehensively

² Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

³ DFG, German Research Foundation - Research data in connection with the funding programmes Link: <https://www.dfg.de/en/principles-dfg-funding/basics-and-principles-of-funding/research-data/research-funding> Accessed 25 June, 2024

documented. The specific elements that need to be shared may vary depending on the research question, academic community, or project specifics.

Data from DFG-funded research should be publicly accessible and free of charge (i.e., open access), enhancing transparency and promoting the widespread dissemination of research findings. If access to data needs to be restricted due to legal, copyright, or ethical reasons, these restrictions must be clearly justified and documented in the DMP. Additionally, to facilitate effective reuse, research data must be quality-assured and extensively described. Proper documentation is essential for the usability and reproducibility of research data. Every research project must include a detailed DMP that comprehensively covers these aspects to ensure compliance and the effective management of research data:

- **Reproducibility:** Detailing the reproducibility of research data and the resources required. Specifying whether research data comes from one-time observations or repeatable experiments.
- **Data Types and Formats:** Clearly identifying the types and formats of data, such as images, audio, text, source code, or numerical data.
- **Data Collection, Analysis, and Processing:** Describing the methods and tools used for data collection, analysis, and processing.
- **File Formats:** Using open or documented file formats whenever possible. If data requires specific software for access, documenting this software or ensuring it is included in the database, provided copyright allows.
- **Data Documentation:** Adhering to common standards for data documentation and description to facilitate understanding and reuse.
- **Data Management, Retention, and Security:** Explaining how data will be managed, retained, and secured throughout the project.
- **Quality Assurance:** Including measures for ensuring the quality of data.
- **Referencing:** Describing how research objects and other data will be referenced.
- **RDM Responsibilities:** Specifying the roles and responsibilities for RDM within the project, in addition to those of the principal investigators.
- **Provision and Discoverability of Data:** Detailing how data will be provided for reuse and the measures taken to ensure its discoverability, accessibility, and reusability. Providing a clear justification if reuse is not possible.
- **Timing of Data Provision:** Indicating when data will be made available for reuse.
- **Conditions for Reuse:** Outlining the conditions for data reuse and any long-term decision-making processes.
- **Costs and Financing:** Identifying the costs associated with RDM during the project and for the provision of data for reuse, and explaining how these costs will be financed.

In certain disciplines, **conference abstracts** may play a crucial role in the research process and should be shared in the interest of good scientific practice. Whether this applies to a specific case depends on the nature of the project. If researchers consider it necessary to share abstracts to enhance the transparency, reproducibility, or traceability of their research results, and if there are no legal or ethical constraints, these abstracts should also be made available in compliance with good scientific practice.

5 DATA DESCRIPTION

The first step in creating an RDMP is to describe the research data in detail. This fundamental step is crucial for effective data management throughout the lifecycle of the project. We expect our subprojects to provide detailed information about the type of research data, data format, data sources and software, and the amount of data.

5.1 DATA TYPE

Subprojects must list all types of data relevant to their projects. RDMP must ensure that all relevant data are accurately named and categorized in this section. Types relevant to the fields of condensed matter physics and materials science and consistent with the DFG categorization of data types include, for example:

- **Measurement data:** Data obtained through measurements with various instruments
- **Visual information:** Images and video recordings
- **Methodological test procedures:** Protocols for preparing samples, recording observations or conducting an experiment
- **Calculations and simulations**
- **Objects/Samples:** Prepared from an external source or in the laboratory
- Software.

Subprojects must provide detailed information on the use of existing data. This includes the source of the data, the conditions of use, and how the existing data will be integrated into the current research project. Existing data refers to data that was previously collected or created for purposes other than the current research project. Examples of existing data include publicly available datasets, published research data, data that has been made available through publications or repositories, archived data, secondary data analysis, etc.

5.2 DATA FORMAT

Subprojects should specify all formats used in their projects. This includes specifying the formats for different types of data such as text documents (e.g., PDF, DOCX), spreadsheets (e.g., XLSX, CSV), images (e.g., JPEG, PNG), audio files (e.g., WAV, MP3), video files (e.g., MP4, AVI), databases (e.g., MySQL, PostgreSQL), and special scientific formats (e.g., HDF5 for scientific data, DICOM for medical imaging). Each format should be clearly documented to ensure compatibility, accessibility, and long-term preservation of the research data.

When selecting data formats suitable for research supported by the DFG-funded research, researchers should be guided by several principles in order to comply with the FAIR principles. First, researchers should prioritize *open formats* that are non-proprietary and widely supported. These formats, such as CSV for tabular data, XML or JSON for structured data, TIFF for images, WAV for audio, and PDF/A for documents, ensure accessibility without the need for special software or licenses.

- CSV: A simple text format, suitable for straightforward structures. It is compact and easy to use.
- XML: Offers versatile options for representing complex structures. It involves a relatively large amount of text due to its markup and hierarchical nature.
- RDF: Provides a way to model complex relationships and is a standard for the "Semantic Web." It is designed to represent data in a way that emphasizes relationships and can be used for more advanced data integration.

To ensure interoperability and reusability of data, researchers should avoid using proprietary file formats commonly used by scientific instrument software. Instead, they should opt for open and non-proprietary formats that are supported by multiple vendors and accessible with various software systems.

Second, researchers should opt for *standardized formats* that comply with international standards. Standards improve interoperability between different systems and ensure the long-term accessibility of data. Examples include HDF5 for scientific data, MPEG for multimedia, and ASCII for text-based data. Third, researchers should choose formats that are *machine-readable* and enable automated processing and analysis. Machine-readable formats allow software tools to interpret, search, validate, and reuse data without manual conversion. Examples include CSV, JSON, XML, RDF, NetCDF, HDF5, and well-structured TXT files with clear delimiters. These formats support the FAIR principle of machine readability and facilitate the efficient integration and reuse of data.

Researchers should adhere to research *community standards* and best practices in their research area. Consistent data formats promote interoperability and facilitate collaboration and data sharing within the research community.

Finally, researchers should employ *version control procedures* for data formats to effectively track changes. Version control ensures data integrity, reproducibility, and transparency throughout the research lifecycle.

By following these guidelines, researchers can ensure that their chosen data formats support effective data management, sharing, and reuse, in line with DFG principles and wider international research standards.

5.3 DATA SOURCES AND SOFTWARE FOR DATA PROCESSING

Subprojects should provide comprehensive information on data sources, including the following guidelines: Data sources include research tools, methodologies, software, or code employed to generate the data, as well as external sources from which the data will be obtained for later use. When describing the research instruments used for data acquisition, it is advisable to include details such as type, model/manufacturer, configuration, specific source-related information, acquisition mode, analysis workflow, and relevant detectors, if any. This comprehensive information facilitates accurate interpretation and efficient management of data throughout the research process.

When describing procedures for sample preparation, recording observations or conducting experiments, it is advisable to include the name, workflow, and reference to a recognized community-approved and published methodology. This ensures the reproducibility of the method and the accurate interpretation of the resulting data.

For calculations and simulations, it is advisable to indicate the computer codes or software used and cite them accordingly. Descriptions and citations of data repositories, publications, online databases, standardization institutes, or vendors should be explicit and detailed. They should include any restrictions or agreements regarding the reuse of data.

Subprojects should provide comprehensive information on the software tools used for data processing in their projects. This includes specifying the names and versions of the software applications used for data collection, analysis, visualization, and other relevant processes. In addition, describing any custom scripts or algorithms developed for data manipulation and analysis would increase clarity and facilitate understanding for future use and collaboration.

5.4 DATA QUANTITY

Subprojects should specify the quantity of each data type in terms of volume (e.g., gigabytes or terabytes) and the number of files. Associate each data type with its quantity and provide an estimated total sum of all data. This estimation aids in assessing storage and backup requirements, as well as potential costs. Carefully project the expected quantity of each data type, considering possible growth or changes. Ensure that storage capacity and backup systems are adequate, and develop a plan for handling unexpected increases in data volume.

6 DOCUMENTATION AND DATA QUALITY

6.1 ORGANIZATION OF DATA

Subprojects should provide detailed information on how their data is organized. A clear structure is important to facilitate access and retrieval. This may include the creation of a systematic folder hierarchy or the use of a database management system. In research fields such as condensed-matter physics and materials science, the structure of a material or system is critical to its properties, and the same principle applies to research data. An effective file naming convention could include the project name, date, and a brief description of the data, e.g., "ProjectX_2024-06-26_Experiment1_RawData.csv"⁴. Such a system ensures that data are well-organized and easily identifiable, enhancing overall data management and accessibility. For data organization in general, we recommend the 5S method: Sort, Set in order, Shine, Standardize, Sustain⁵. The 5S method is a systematic approach to workplace organization aimed at improving efficiency and reducing waste. It consists of five steps:

- **Sort:** Eliminate unnecessary items from the workspace, keeping only what is essential for daily operations to reduce clutter and distractions.
- **Set in Order:** Arrange necessary items for easy access and use, ensuring tools and materials have designated places for streamlined workflow.
- **Shine:** Clean the workspace regularly to maintain a tidy and safe environment, while also inspecting equipment and facilities for issues.
- **Standardize:** Establish consistent practices and procedures for tasks to ensure uniformity and efficiency across the workplace.
- **Sustain:** Maintain and continuously improve the 5S processes through regular training, audits, and involvement of all team members to embed these practices into the organizational culture.

6.2 DOCUMENTATION

Subprojects should provide information on their data documentation procedures and ensure that detailed records are kept using appropriate tools to ensure the integrity and usability of the data. This also includes how the data was collected, processed, and analyzed.

For experimental work, traceable documentation of the data implies explanations of standardized measurement protocols that have been developed based on the specific requirements of the applicants. These protocols must clearly outline the chronological sequence of measurements for a sample, the total number of measurements, and any exclusion of measurement data, including the reason for exclusion and the location where the samples are archived.

⁴ As a guideline see: Data Carpentry: File Organization Lesson - <https://datacarpentry.org/rr-organization1/>

⁵ 5S Data - Kompetenznetzwerk Forschungsdatenmanagement Thüringen, <https://forschungsdaten-thueringen.de/5s-data-de/articles/5s-data.html> Accessed 25 June, 2024

Primary data must be saved on the measurement, testing, or production computers and then transferred to evaluation computers along with the associated metadata. Manually or analogously recorded measurement data must be digitized and documented with their metadata. At a minimum, the documentation for each sample must include the measurement or analysis devices used, the sample material, and the measurement date. The samples themselves must be archived in a way that ensures they can be easily located.

The final storage of data should occur on a different system with a backup concept and the capability for long-term data archiving.⁶

To ensure efficient data organization and documentation, it is essential to develop and implement a thorough strategy including the choice of appropriate tools and methodologies. It is advisable to store digital data in a structured form (in key-value pairs) to facilitate subsequent conversion into machine-readable formats (e.g., CSV, JSON).

Electronic Labor Notebooks (ELNs) can support structured documentation of laboratory workflows, experiments, samples, and metadata. However, CRC 1615 does not coordinate an independent ELN rollout. TUHH is responsible for developing and coordinating a broader institutional ELN solution. CRC 1615 follows this development and aligns its RDM support with the institutional solution where relevant.

Other websites to find suitable ELNs:

- [Documenting research data: Electronic Lab\(oratory\) Notebooks | ZB MED - Informationszentrum Lebenswissenschaften \(publisso.de\): https://www.publisso.de/en/research-data-management/rd-documenting](https://www.publisso.de/en/research-data-management/rd-documenting)
- [ELN-Finder :: Home \(tu-darmstadt.de\): https://eln-finder.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/home](https://eln-finder.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/home)

Other forms of documentation are:

- README files⁷
- Data Dictionaries⁸
- Codebooks
- Articles in a Data Journal such as [ing.grid](#), [Data in brief](#) or [Journal of Open Research Software](#)

Data documentation usually includes the following aspects:

- Persons involved, place, date, time, context, project history, intention/objective, hypotheses
- Methods, circumstances of the survey, technical framework, devices
- Data structures, relationships between objects
- Value ranges, quality criteria, validity
- Changes in the course of the project, versioning
- Legal issues/access
- Names, designations for variables and their values, units,
- Explanations of codes, classification schemes, terminologies, definitions
- Coding of missing values/reasons for missing values
- Derived data, algorithms used, weightings

To guarantee thorough documentation of data and comprehensive metadata, it is important to employ standard formats and vocabularies endorsed by your community. This facilitates understanding and

⁶ DFG - Fachforum Materialwissenschaft und Werkstofftechnik, [fk-materialwissenschaft-werkstofftechnik-2023-data.pdf \(dfg.de\)](#) Accessed 09 July, 2024

⁷ Guidelines for creating readme style metadata, <https://www5.open.ac.uk/library-research-support/sites/www.open.ac.uk.library-research-support/files/files/RDM-Guidelines-for-creating-readme-style-metadata.pdf> Accessed 09 July, 2024

⁸ See Bowman, S. How to Make a Data Dictionary. <https://help.osf.io/article/217-how-to-make-a-data-dictionary>. Accessed 28 June, 2024

utilization of your data and written documentation by others. Furthermore, details on the origin of the data, such as origin, time of creation, and processing method.

6.3 LINKING DATA WITH EXTENSIVE METADATA

Subprojects must provide comprehensive metadata for all research data intended for storage, publication, and reuse. Metadata describe the context, structure, provenance, and meaning of data objects and are therefore essential for interpretation, quality assurance, long-term accessibility, and reuse. In line with DFG expectations for good research practice and research data management, metadata should be planned early, documented continuously, and made available together with the data whenever possible.

The main TUHH repository, TORE, provides essential repository-level metadata for published research outputs, such as title, creator, publication date, abstract, keywords, license, persistent identifiers, and citation information. These metadata support discoverability, citation, and long-term access. However, TORE does not provide discipline-specific metadata for all possible data types, methods, instruments, experimental workflows, or domain vocabularies. Therefore, subprojects remain responsible for preparing detailed subject-specific metadata that explain how the data were generated, processed, analyzed, and should be interpreted.

Each subproject should develop a suitable metadata approach for its own data types, methods, and research community. The already conducted interviews in SMART Reactors have shown that a single common data format or metadata schema cannot adequately cover all subprojects, as the data types, methods, and workflows are too heterogeneous. Therefore, subprojects should use widely accepted ontologies, vocabularies, and metadata standards from their respective research communities whenever available. If no established standard exists, researchers should review related projects, publications, repositories, and community recommendations to identify appropriate metadata practices.

For engineering and experimental research, Metadata4Ing provides a useful ontology for describing the generation of research data within scientific activities. Subprojects should review the Metadata4Ing website, with particular attention to the general process model, as it helps structure metadata around objects, actors, processes, tools, and results. The NFDI4Ing Metadata Profile Service and the NFDI4Ing Terminology Service can also support the identification of relevant engineering-related metadata profiles, ontologies, and controlled vocabularies.

In experimental research, metadata for sample synthesis, preparation, measurements, and analysis should include detailed documentation of all relevant steps. This may include ingredients, materials, sample identifiers, environmental conditions, time duration, instrument type and configuration, calibration information, software used, processing scripts, measurement settings, and quality control procedures. For measurement data, metadata should describe the type of measurement, the physical properties measured, the instrument used, relevant settings, the duration and timing of the measurement, and the state or history of the sample at the time of measurement.

A systematic overview of metadata schema is provided by Data Cite Commons (<https://schema.datacite.org/>) and also by NFD4Ing/ Metadata4Ing.

Regardless of the specific project, the following information is generally important for metadata:

- **Objects:** Metadata should describe and identify the objects generated, processed, or used during the workflow. Without clear and persistent identification, linking and utilizing additional information becomes challenging. *Example: In material science research, a unique identifier for a synthesized compound ensures all related data, such as its characterization or test results, are correctly associated.*

- **Actors:** Actors can include individuals, groups, or organizations involved in the creation and processing of data, as well as technical systems that initiate or execute actions. This is particularly important for accounting and security purposes.
- **Sources:** Document the context in which data were generated, including the location, time, and circumstances of collection, along with the actors (persons or systems) involved. *Example: When studying the properties of a new alloy, the metadata might include the laboratory location, the date of the experiment, and the equipment used to measure thermal conductivity.*
- **Processes:** It can be useful to document the processing steps that data underwent, detailing which actors-initiated actions, the programs and systems used, and the timeline of these events. *Example: Metadata could track the series of heat treatments applied to a material, including the software used to monitor temperature changes and the exact times these processes occurred.*
- **Results:** The final data intended for direct use, which are of primary relevance for future reuse, should be discoverable through metadata and may need to be enriched for presentation. *Example: In a study on nanomaterials, the final data set describing particle size distribution might be accompanied by metadata explaining how the measurements were taken and how the data should be interpreted.*

Here are some other recommended reputable sources and websites that address metadata standards and best practices:

- NFDI4Ing Metadata Profile Service

Website: [The NFDI4Ing Metadata Profile Service - NFDI4Ing](#)

Domain-Specific Repositories and Organizations: Depending on the research discipline, domain-specific repositories and organizations often provide metadata standards tailored to specific fields of study. For example:

- NFDI4Ing Terminology Services: 96 ontologies used in engineering sciences:

Website: <https://terminology.nfdi4ing.de/ts/>

- GenBank (for molecular biology): Provides metadata standards for genetic sequence data.

Website: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/>

- ICSU World Data System (WDS): Offers metadata standards for environmental and earth sciences data.

Website: <https://www.icsu-wds.org/>

Research Data Alliance (RDA): The RDA provides community-driven recommendations and guidelines for RDM, including metadata standards. On their Web site, you will find working and interest groups dealing with metadata, where researchers can find relevant standards and recommendations.

Website: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

DataCite: DataCite is an international organization that provides persistent identifiers (DOIs) for research data and promotes citation standards for data. It provides guidelines and tools for the creation and management of metadata to improve the discoverability and accessibility of data.

Website: <https://www.datacite.org/>

Digital Curation Centre (DCC): The DCC provides resources and guidance on digital curation, including metadata standards and best practices. Their Web site provides valuable tools, case studies, and training materials for researchers.

Website: <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/>

6.4 QUALITY ASSESSMENT

Subprojects should provide comprehensive information on how they maintain data quality. They should develop a robust quality assurance strategy to guarantee the reliability and accuracy of their data. This might involve automated data checks, manual reviews, or data validation protocols. Ensuring the quality of research data through quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) is fundamental to any research endeavor. It guarantees that the data gathered meet rigorous standards, which increases the credibility and trustworthiness of the research findings. It is therefore essential that researchers outline in their RDMP the methodologies and tools they intend to utilize for maintaining high data quality. According to the DFG Code of Conduct, it is mandatory to explain the quality assurance mechanisms used when research results are publicly disseminated (Guideline 7)⁹.

To maintain the integrity of your data, it is essential to establish the standards or protocols utilized in your research for gauging, evaluating, and enhancing data quality. These protocols may involve routine data evaluations, error rectification, and validation against recognized standards or guidelines.

Moreover, it is fundamental to detail the frequency and protocol for instrument calibration, conditioning, and verification tests to guarantee precise data acquisition. Additionally, enumerate the statistical and visualization methods you employ to identify errors in the data. Furthermore, acknowledge any community standards adhered to in conducting and reporting experimental and computational results. Adhering to these guidelines will uphold the high quality and compliance of your research data, fostering trust and reproducibility in your work while averting the dissemination of inaccurate or erroneous conclusions.

7 STORAGE AND TECHNICAL ARCHIVING

Data storage is a critical process that aims to securely protect research data to ensure its long-term availability and accessibility. *As mandated by the DFG, research data must be stored at least ten years after the completion of a project*¹⁰. This period ensures that valuable research outputs remain accessible for future reference, replication, and reuse. Effective data preservation strategies encompass robust storage solutions, systematic backup procedures, and adherence to standards that promote data integrity and longevity. By implementing comprehensive preservation measures, research institutions and projects not only comply with regulatory requirements but also contribute to the continuity and transparency of scientific knowledge.

A structured data storage system is currently¹¹ being established in SMART Reactors to facilitate data sharing.

7.1 TORE AS MAIN REPOSITORY

The CRC designates TORE as its primary repository for research data. The TUHH library is currently working on extending TORE so that it can store large amounts of data. Detailed, step-by-step instructions for data submission are provided in the TORE Help.

1. [How to Publish Research Data on TORE](#)
2. [How to Index Research Data in TORE](#)
3. [After Publishing: Create a New Version](#)

⁹ German Research Foundation (DFG). Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice Code of Conduct, <https://wissenschaftliche-integritaet.de/en/> Accessed 25 June, 2024

¹⁰ DFG Guidelines on the Handling of Research Data: <https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/172098/b08fcad16f1ff5ddca967f1ebde3a8c3/guidelines-research-data-data.pdf> Accessed 30 July, 2024

¹¹ As of 23 July, 2026

Projects are allowed to utilize their own repositories, as long as they support data accessibility for both internal project members and the public. Therefore, appropriate access controls must be implemented to accommodate varying levels of data accessibility. Additionally, TORE should be capable of referencing these repositories. It is essential that any repository chosen can meet the data delivery timelines mandated by the DFG. Preparing data for deposition into a storage entails adhering to specified requirements for file formats, metadata schemas, and licensing agreements. These measures ensure that data remains accessible, compliant, and interoperable according to established standards. [Zenodo](#) may be used as a complementary repository for code and software, especially when software-specific versioning, GitHub/GitLab integration, releases, and citation metadata are needed. Zenodo currently supports up to 50 GB per record and up to 100 files, with a one-time quota increase up to 200 GB possible.

[Chemotion](#) is recommended for suitable chemical research data, especially where structured chemistry-specific documentation and publication are needed. [NFDI4Chem](#) supports FAIR collection, storage, processing, publication, and reuse of chemistry research data.

Where data are published in Zenodo, Chemotion, or another suitable domain repository, the publication should still be linked through TORE to maintain a central CRC 1615 overview.

Researchers should provide information on archiving throughout the subproject's duration and after its completion, taking into account the 10-year retention period mentioned above. The aim is to facilitate data accessibility for the project team and external collaborators while safeguarding against data loss resulting from unforeseen events like hardware failures, theft, or natural calamities.

7.2 BACKUP

Commence by outlining the approach for storing and backing up research data. As a standard practice, it is advisable to retain three copies of data, employing at least two distinct storage mediums. One of these duplicates should be housed in a physically segregated location to mitigate risks from unexpected events. Subprojects should determine the backup frequency based on data sensitivity and the complexity of replacing them in the event of data loss. Additionally, researchers should provide details on the backup procedures utilized.

The backup methods can be categorized as follows:

1. **Full Backup:** This involves copying all files during each backup session.
2. **Incremental Backup:** Only files that have been added or modified since the previous backup are copied.
3. **Differential Backup:** Files that have been added or changed since the last full backup are copied.

Specify whether the backup process will be conducted manually or automatically (recommended), along with the frequency of testing the backups. We also endorse the **3-2-1 rule** as recommended by forschungsdaten.info.¹²

For keeping the different copies of data in line with each other, i.e., to avoid outdated data and/or version conflicts, look up according synchronization tools for the used operating system.

Alongside digital data, the storage of physical data, like samples, warrants consideration. In such instances, the storage strategy should detail the physical medium and its location, along with any requisite storage conditions for sample preservation, such as humidity and temperature controls. For instance, will the samples be housed in a nitrogen glovebox, vacuum desiccator, special encapsulation,

¹² Datensicherheit und Backup | Speichern und Rechnen | Themen | Forschungsdaten und Forschungsdatenmanagement, <https://forschungsdaten.info/themen/speichern-und-rechnen/datensicherheit-und-backup/> Accessed 26 June, 2024

or an ultra-high vacuum chamber? Additionally, elucidate on the stability of physical samples and their degradation over time.

Furthermore, outline the access and usage rights pertaining to the stored and archived data throughout the project's lifespan, particularly if multiple project members and collaborators are involved.

8 DATA EXCHANGE

Data exchange includes both internal data sharing within the CRC and external publication or provision of research data beyond the CRC. Subprojects should outline in their RDMP which data will be shared internally during the research process, which data will be published externally, and whether access will be provided immediately or after a defined embargo period.

Embargo periods may be necessary to protect data during manuscript preparation, industrial collaborations, confidentiality obligations, or planned patent applications. Any restrictions, embargoes, or access conditions should be clearly justified and documented in the RDMP¹³.

8.1 INTERNAL DATA EXCHANGE WITHIN THE CRC

For internal collaboration, the CRC Data Exchange platform will be made available soon. This platform is intended to support secure and structured data exchange between CRC subprojects before data are ready for public publication. It should be used for collaborative work, quality checks, joint analysis, internal review, and the controlled exchange of project-related data within the CRC.

Internal data exchange does not replace formal publication in a repository. Rather, it supports ongoing research collaboration and helps prepare data, metadata, documentation, and related materials for later publication where appropriate. Subprojects should use the CRC Data Exchange platform to make relevant working data available to project partners in a secure and traceable way, especially when data are needed for cross-subproject collaboration.

Access to internally shared data should be managed according to the sensitivity of the data and the needs of the respective collaboration. If data are confidential, restricted, or subject to contractual, legal, ethical, or voluntary limitations, access should be limited accordingly. Responsibilities for data upload, versioning, documentation, and access control should be clarified within the subproject and, where needed, coordinated with the data steward.

8.2 EXTERNAL DATA EXCHANGE AND PUBLICATION

As a CRC funded by the DFG, our approach to information and data sharing prioritizes openness whenever feasible. The CRC should share data openly by default, while keeping specific datasets closed only when necessary due to legal, contractual, ethical, technical, or voluntary restrictions.

Data intended for external reuse should be made accessible by depositing them in a suitable repository, as described in Section 6. Data should be published together with the necessary metadata, documentation, methods, and software tools required to access, understand, and reuse them. Documentation should clearly specify which software is needed to open, process, or analyze the files. Where possible, relevant software, scripts, and open-source code should be deposited together with the data or linked through persistent identifiers.

¹³ "FAIRmat, Guide to Writing a Research Data Management Plan", version 1.0, Accessed 25 June, 2024 Link: [FAIRmat%20DMP%20guide%2022%20May%202023.pdf \(fairmat-nfdi.eu\)](https://www.fairmat-nfdi.eu/FAIRmat%20DMP%20guide%2022%20May%202023.pdf)

TORE is the main TUHH repository and is suitable for datasets and research artifacts intended for publication. Published outputs in TORE receive a DOI, supporting citation, long-term availability, and discoverability. TORE should therefore be used for finalized datasets, documentation, and research outputs that are intended to be publicly accessible or formally archived.

While TORE also supports software publications, we recommend using Zenodo for software developed and maintained through tools such as GitHub or GitLab, as Zenodo better supports software versioning and integration with these development platforms. After publication in Zenodo, subprojects can add the relevant metadata and links to the software publication in TORE.

A short overview of publication options through TORE and Zenodo, including the TUHH Community, is available here: <https://www.tub.tuhh.de/en/publishing/research-data/publish-research-data/>

If data cannot be made openly available, access should be provided in accordance with the applicable restrictions. This may involve controlled access procedures, consultation with the data steward, or specific agreements with data users. Conditions for access should be clearly described and, where possible, supported by a machine-readable license or access statement. The identity of individuals requesting access may need to be verified to ensure secure, responsible, and appropriate data sharing. In summary, the CRC Data Exchange platform should be used for secure internal data sharing during the research process, while TORE and, where appropriate, Zenodo should be used for external publication and long-term availability of finalized research outputs. Internal data exchange supports collaboration; external publication supports openness, citation, and DFG-compliant research data management.

9 LEGAL OBLIGATIONS

In the case of utilizing copyrighted data, where it is anticipated that the data will be made available to other researchers for reuse within the context of a research data publication following exclusive use by the authors or rights holders, it is recommended to specify the duration of exclusive use, i.e., the timing of the publication of the research data, in the RDMP.

Prior to commencing the research process, it is imperative to have a comprehensive understanding of legal considerations and any pertinent details.

9.1 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTIES AND COPYRIGHTS

In principle, research data in Germany is subject to copyright law. However, copyright protection only applies when a work meets the requirements of personal creation, perceptible form, intellectual content, and individual character. For research data, this is not always the case (e.g., with unstructured measurement data), meaning that such data is often not protected by copyright¹⁴. Researchers should clarify whether the project is expected to yield any products safeguarded by intellectual property rights and specify the relevant laws and policies governing them. This aspect is particularly critical for patents, proprietary software, or commercialized goods.

Copyright laws pertain to original works of authorship, encompassing scientific publications and various research outputs. Researchers must ensure compliance with copyright regulations when disseminating or sharing their research outputs.

¹⁴ [Copyright law of Germany - Wikipedia](#) Accessed 19 August, 2024

9.2 DATA LICENSE

Researchers should carefully deliberate which data license to apply to their research data, as it delineates the terms and conditions for data use and distribution. There is now a wide range of licensing models available for establishing usage rights, but a detailed explanation of these would go beyond the scope of this handbook. Selecting a license that aligns with data-sharing objectives and adheres to legal requirements is imperative. Researchers in the CRC should acknowledge and address legal considerations pertaining to research data to ensure compliance with pertinent laws and policies. By incorporating legal aspects into their data management plan, researchers can preempt potential legal challenges and guarantee proper management of their research data.

One way to determine which license best suits your research data is to use the following checklist to identify your specific requirements:

- Who owns the data and is authorized to publish it?
- Does the chosen license allow for comprehensive reuse of the data?
- Can interested parties easily identify ownership and the required citation format?
- Has the potential economic value of the data been considered (e.g., patent rights)?
- Is each part of the work licensed optimally (e.g., images, software, data)? Is it necessary to apply the same restrictions to every part of the work?

9.3 EXISTING FREE LICENSES:

[Creative Commons \(CC\)](#): They can be used for text, images, etc. For data, it is generally recommended to use version 4.0 and higher.

Some of the most common CC licenses are:

- **CC0 (No Rights Reserved, Public Domain)**: CC0 is especially useful for sharing data and databases, as it clarifies the rights related to factual data that might not be covered by copyright. While databases can include factual information that is not copyright-protected, CC0 ensures unrestricted use. Many organizations recommend using CC0 for tabular data and databases, particularly for scientific data. Although CC0 does not legally require users to cite the source, it maintains the moral obligation to provide attribution, as is standard in scientific research.
- **CC-BY (Attribution)**: Licensing research outputs under CC-BY ensures open access while requiring that users credit the producers/authors with a citation when they use or refer to your work. This license allows others to distribute, remix, modify, and build upon existing work and data—even for commercial purposes—provided they credit the original creator. CC-BY is very flexible and is recommended for maximizing the dissemination and use of research outputs.
- **CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)**: This license allows others to remix, modify, and build upon research work, including for commercial purposes, as long as they credit the producers/authors and license their new creations under the same terms. Similar to “copyleft” free and open-source software licenses, it ensures that all new works will carry the same license, allowing commercial use of derivatives.
- **CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)**: This license allows research work to be redistributed, both commercially and non-commercially, as long as it remains unchanged and intact, with proper credit given to the creator. This ensures the work can be shared widely without alterations, preserving its original form while acknowledging the original contribution.

Other licenses are:

- [Open Data Commons \(ODC\)](#): In particular for data collections.
- [GNU General Public License \(GPL\)](#): Especially for software

10 RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES

Please note that DFG mandates the storage of data for a minimum of 10 years or longer (as pointed out above). Therefore, assigning responsibility to a PhD student who will depart SMART Reactors in a short time is not advisable. If this option is chosen, ensure that a) each subproject has a secondary data manager and b) a clear plan for handover to another individual is established from the project's inception. At the end of the day, the Principal Investigator is responsible for the RDM and will be held liable for not complying with the DFG rules.

This handbook is intended to complement existing guidelines, such as:

the Guidelines for Handling Research Data (DFG):

https://www.dfg.de/download/pdf/foerderung/grundlagen_dfg_foerderung/forschungsdaten/leitlinien_forschungsdaten.pdf

Subject-Specific Recommendations on the Handling of Research Data (DFG):

<https://www.dfg.de/en/principles-dfg-funding/basics-and-principles-of-funding/research-data/recommendations>

FAIRMAT Guide to Writing RDMP:

<https://www.fairmat-nfdi.eu/uploads/Area%20FAIRmat%2520DMP%2520guide%252022%2520May%25202023.pdf>

The Codex, Guidelines for Ensuring Good Scientific Practice:

<https://wissenschaftliche-integritaet.de/>